

Co-ordination Compounds of Diaryltin Dihalides with Certain Amides

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The interaction of diaryltin dihalides with certain amides yields molecular adducts of the formula $R_2SnX_2 \cdot nL$ ($R = \text{phenyl-, } o\text{-, } m\text{-, or } p\text{-tolyl, } X = \text{Cl or Br, and } L = \text{an amide molecule, } n = 1 \text{ or } 2$), which have been characterised by elemental analysis and infrared spectral studies.

CONTINUING our investigations on the acceptor property of various diaryltin dihalides towards formamide, acetamide and their substituted derivatives^{1,2} we have prepared some new molecular adducts of these Lewis acids with certain other amides and the results are reported in this short communication.

Experimental

Diphenyltin dichloride, dibromide, di-*o*-tolyltin, and di-*p*-tolyltin dichlorides were prepared according to the reported procedure³. Benzamide (B), *N*-benzyl benzamide (NBB), *N*-phenyl acetamide (NPA), and dimethyl propionamide (DMP) were obtained from Aldrich chemicals and recrystallised from suitable solvent before use.

The elemental analysis (C, H, and N) was carried out by the semi-micro technique at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow and the tin was determined gravimetrically as SnO_2 . The molecular weight of typical complexes was determined cryoscopically in benzene and the molar conductance of $10^{-3}M$ solution in anhydrous nitrobenzene at 30° was measured using Phillips conductivity assembly PR 9500. The infrared spectra of the free Lewis bases and their complexes were recorded in Nujol on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer model 521 in the range 4000–200 cm^{-1} at the Chemical Laboratory of the McGill University, Montreal, Canada.

The antimicrobial activity of the Lewis acids, bases, and their adducts was examined against certain fungi such as *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, *Trycophyton mentagraphytes*, *Mycobacterium canis* and *Aspergillus niger* and bacteria such as *Bisillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Escherichia coli* by two fold serial dilution method⁴.

Preparation of complexes

In a typical reaction, 2 mmole of diaryltin dihalide was refluxed with an appropriate quantity of the Lewis base in chloroform or petroleum ether (60°–80°)

for 2 hr. On removing excess solvent and cooling, a white crystalline solid was obtained which was washed with diethylether, dried under vacuum and analysed.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data of the complexes and the relevant infrared absorption frequencies in their spectra are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

The complexes are white crystalline solids, thermally stable, soluble in common organic solvents and insensitive to atmospheric moisture except the (*p*-tolyl)₂SnCl₂·2DMP which is appreciably hygroscopic. Abnormally low values for the molecular weight than calculated from the formulae weight, indicate significant dissociation of the complexes in solution and molar conductance of 1.9 mhos.cm²/mole of $10^{-3}M$ solution in nitrobenzene suggest absence of ionic species. The interaction of these complexes with strong electron donor molecules such as 2,2'-bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, dimethyl sulfoxide and pyridine *N*-oxide resulted in complete displacement of the amide molecule, which indicate weaker electron donating ability of the amides. The antimicrobial activity of the complexes was almost of the same order as that of the parent Lewis acids in equivalent concentration. The co-ordination, therefore, seems to have no effect on the biological activity of organotin halides as reported earlier⁴.

Infrared spectra

The negative shift of the absorptions associated with the stretching and deformation modes of the C=O group and a positive shift of the bands due to $\nu C=N$ vibration and the deformation of $-N=C=O$ in the spectra of all the complexes from those in corresponding free Lewis bases indicate co-ordination from oxygen atom of the carbonyl group to the tin atom^{1,2}. The identification of a band at $345 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of all the adducts but absent in those of the Lewis acids or bases is attributed to Sn–O stretching

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TABLE 1--EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR THE ADDUCTS OF DIARYLTIN DIHALIDES

Adduct	m.p. (°C)	Analysis % Found (Calcd)			
		Sn	C	H	N
1. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .2B	116-18	20.21 (20.27)	53.11 (53.27)	4.31 (4.09)	4.82 (4.78)
2. Ph ₂ SnBr ₂ .2B	126-28	17.23 (17.59)	46.30 (46.24)	3.31 (3.55)	4.14 (4.16)
3. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .NPA	101-02	24.24 (24.84)	50.04 (50.10)	3.86 (3.06)	2.76 (2.92)
4. Ph ₂ SnBr ₂ .NPA	110-13	20.23 (20.95)	41.98 (42.26)	3.12 (3.34)	2.12 (2.46)
5. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .NBB	74	20.91 (21.44)	56.62 (56.21)	4.62 (4.14)	2.81 (2.52)
6. (o-tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .NBB	75-77	20.22 (20.40)	57.31 (57.63)	2.22 (2.91)	3.51 (2.40)
7. Ph ₂ SnCl ₂ .DMP	54-55	26.90 (26.51)	45.71 (45.84)	4.91 (4.71)	3.02 (3.14)
8. Ph ₂ SnBr ₂ .DMP	61-63	22.01 (22.28)	38.51 (38.20)	3.62 (3.93)	2.51 (2.62)
9. (o-tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .DMP	76-77	24.61 (25.15)	48.01 (48.20)	5.02 (5.28)	3.21 (2.95)
10. (p-tolyl) ₂ SnCl ₂ .DMP	64-68	24.61 (25.15)	— (48.20)	— (5.28)	— (2.95)

 TABLE 2--RELEVANT INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (CM⁻¹) IN FREE LEWIS BASES AND THEIR ADDUCTS WITH DIARYLTIN DIHALIDES

Compound	ν C=O	ν C-N	ν N-C=O	ν C=O	ν Sn-O	ν Sn-Cl	ν Sn-Ph asym.	sym.
B	1675 vs	1295 s	637 vs	531 s				
1	1643 vs	1310 s	652 vs	522 s	352 sb 345 m	275 m	293 m	243 m
2	1640 vs	1307 s	656 vs	519 s	234 m	—	295 m	238 m
NPA	1660 vs	1277 s	663 m	609 m				
3	1622 vs	1332 s	673 m	604 w	355 sh 340 m	272 m	288 m	234 m
4	1618 vs	1334 s	671 m	600 w	353 sh 338 m	—	283 m	231 m
NBB	1634 vs	1260 s	622 s	525 s				
5	1600 vs	1276 s	636 s	512 s	348 sh 340 m	275 m	281 m	237 m
6	1597 vs	1272 s	638 s	514 s	340 m	274 m	279 m	233 m
DMP	1628 vs	1260 s	630 s	540 m				
7	1587 vs	1300 s	645 m	530 w	355 m 335 m	260 m	288 w	230 w
8	1588 vs	1301 s	640 m	525 w	350 m	—	280 m	245 m
9	1587 vs	1298 s	642 m	538 w	349 m	263 m	282 m	235 m
10	1592 vs	1302 s	650 m	532 w	353 m 337 m	272 m	286 m	239 m

Sr. nos. in column 1 refer to complexes in Table 1. s = strong, v = very, m = medium, w = weak.

mode which strongly supports Sn-O bonding in the adducts^{1,2,5-6}.

Two distinct absorptions due to asymmetric and symmetric stretchings of the Sn-X band have been identified in the spectra of unco-ordinated diaryltin dihalides ($\nu_{\text{Sn-Cl}} = 364, 356$; $\nu_{\text{Sn-Br}} = 252, 242$)⁷. In the spectra of the corresponding adducts, only one band attributable to $\nu_{\text{Sn-Cl}}$ could be identified at about 100 cm^{-1} lower than that in the parent Lewis acids. Such lowering of this absorption is characteristic of the increase in the co-ordination number of the tin atom^{5,7}. A similar shift of $\nu_{\text{Sn-X}}$ has been observed on co-ordination by several workers^{8,10}. The absorption due to $\nu_{\text{Sn-Br}}$ could not be identified in the spectra of our diphenyltin dibromide complexes since it is expected to shift beyond the recording range of the instrument. The absorptions at 287 ± 8 and $236 \pm 6 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ consistently occurring in the spectra of all the adducts is attributed to asymmetric and symmetric stretchings of the Sn-C (aromatic) band respectively and appear to be insensitive to co-ordination^{9,10} since they absorb at almost the same position in the spectra of the free Lewis acids^{1,2}.

All complexes excepting those of benzamide possess 1 : 1 stoichiometry and are apparently penta co-ordinated while the adducts of benzamide are hexa-co-ordinated and are likely to have distorted octahedral geometry as reported by Liengme *et al*¹¹.

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